

Institutions, Inclusive Growth And Development In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the multifaceted relationship among institutional frameworks, economic inclusivity, and overall national development. Nigeria, as a dynamic African economy, has experienced a complex trajectory of growth and development, marked by both successes and challenges. The study employed a multidimensional approach, incorporating economic, political, and social perspectives to analyze the role of institutions in shaping the inclusivity of growth. It investigated how the institutional environment, including legal frameworks, governance structures, and regulatory systems, influences the distribution of benefits across various segments of society. Furthermore, the study assessed the implications of inclusive growth on the overall development trajectory of Nigeria. It explores the linkages between inclusive economic policies and sustainable development, considering factors such as poverty alleviation, job creation, and social cohesion. Also, the study investigated the feedback loop between inclusive development and the strengthening of institutions. Methodologically, the study employs a qualitative analysis, drawing on a comprehensive empirical studies, institutional performance metrics, and socio-economic outcomes. By utilizing a diverse range of sources, including government reports, academic literature, and empirical data, the study aims to provide a robust and in-depth understanding of the interdependence between institutions, inclusive growth, and development in Nigeria. The study found that poor governance and corruption as major barriers to inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended the promotion of good governance and strengthening of the anti-corruption agencies.

Keywords: Institutional quality, financial inclusion, Social services, Social protection, Human capital development, Poverty reduction.

JEL Code: E24, E71, I15, I25 I31.

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been growing recognition of the importance of institutions in driving inclusive growth and development in several countries. Institutions provide the necessary framework to ensure stability, fairness and accountability in economic and political systems. Moreover they provide an enabling environment for businesses to thrive attract investments and foster innovation. Okonkwo, Kalu & Nwosu, (2018) found that well-functioning institutions positively influence economic growth and development by reducing transaction costs encouraging efficient resource allocation and attracting foreign direct investment. In addition Yinusa, Aworinde, & Odusanya,

(2020) documented that institutions characterized by transparency, accountability and good governance are essential for achieving inclusive growth and reducing poverty In Nigeria.

In recent years Nigeria has experienced significant growth and transformation for which the oil industry has played a crucial part in Nigeria's economic growth. Metu, Madichie, Anyanwu, Kalu, & Ihugba, (2021) highlights how the discovery of oil in the 1950s transformed Nigeria from an agrarian economy to one heavily dependent on oil exports. Furthermore, studies suggest that the adoption of market-oriented economic policies, such as trade liberalization and privatization, have also contributed to the country's economic growth (Okon, 2018; Okonkwo, Kalu & Nwosu, 2018). These policies aimed at reducing government interference and promoting private sector participation, leading to increased foreign investments and economic diversification.

Institutional factors play a critical part in promoting inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. Empirical studies have shown that institutions such as the legal system, property rights and governance mechanisms significantly influence economic growth and development in a country (Olanrewaju, Aremo, & Binuyo, 2020; Ogujiuba, & Alehile, 2011). In the area of property rights a robust legal system and secure property rights encourage investment and entrepreneurship which leads ultimately to economic growth and the reduction of poverty. In addition effective governance mechanisms such as accountability and the rule of law are necessary in creating an enabling environment for inclusive development. By promoting equal opportunities, reducing corruption and ensuring fairness, institutions in Nigeria can foster inclusive growth and development thereby creating a more prosperous society.

In addition to theoretical arguments, empirical studies provide evidence on the part of institutions in promoting inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. Abiloro, Olawole, & Adeniran, (2020) investigated the relationship between institutions and income inequality in Nigeria using panel data analysis. The findings suggested that improvements in institutions such as rule of law and control of corruption are associated with lower income inequality; while Yinusa, Aworinde, & Odusanya, (2020) investigated the effect of institutional factors on economic growth in Nigeria. The results indicated that good governance and regulatory quality are positively linked to economic development. These demonstrated the importance of institutions in fostering inclusive growth and development in Nigeria highlighting the need for policy interventions to improve institutional quality.

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the multifaceted relationship among institutional frameworks, economic inclusiveness and overall development in Nigeria. It investigated how the institutional environment, including legal frameworks, governance structures, and regulatory systems, influences the distribution of benefits across various

segments of society.

2. INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR ROLE IN INCLUSIVE GROWTH

Institutions play an important role in promoting inclusive growth within a country. These institutions which include legal systems property rights protections and regulatory frameworks provide a conducive environment for innovation, investment and entrepreneurship. The institution's quality enhances the efficiency of resource allocation, reduces corruption and promotes political stability. Improving institutional quality is essential for achieving inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Types of Institutions

An institution can be defined as a set of rules, norms and procedures that guide behavior and shape interactions among individuals and groups within a society (Baland, Bourguignon, Platteau, & Verdier, 2020). Institutions can refer both to formal and informal arrangements that serve as the building blocks of social order in a broader sense. There are various types of institutions that are crucial for inclusive growth and growth in Nigeria. These include political institutions such as the government and political parties which play an important role in shaping public policies and ensuring stability. Economic institutions such as banks and financial systems are essential for promoting economic growth and facilitating trade and investment. Social institutions such as education and healthcare are crucial for the well-being and human capital development of individuals (North, 1991).

The Relationship between Institutions and Economic Development

Empirical studies have provided evidence of a positive relationship between the institutions and economic development. North, (1991) found that countries with inclusive institutions such as secure property rights and the rule of law tend to have higher levels of economic growth. Similarly Michael, & Sharon, (2014) showed that countries with well-established institutions such as strong property rights and contract enforcement experience higher levels of total factor productivity and economic growth. Further, Flachaire, García-Peñalosa, & Konte, (2011) found that institutions especially those that support political stability and government effectiveness are important determinants of economic growth.

Importance of inclusive institutions for sustainable development

Inclusive institutions are important for sustainable development because they promote economic growth and reduce poverty. Studies have shown that countries with more inclusive institutions tend to make higher levels of economic growth and enjoy more just distribution of resources (Olanrewaju, Aremo, & Binuyo, 2020)). Inclusive institutions provide an even working field for all individuals regardless of their background or socio-economic status by

promoting opportunities, protecting property rights ensuring access to basic services and promoting social cohesion (Orhan, 2016; Baland, et al., 2020). These institutions also enhance transparency and accountability which are vital for promoting confidence and trust attracting investment and reducing corruption. Inclusive institutions contribute to the promotion and improvement of a sustainable economic development and the overall well being of a society. Strong institutions contribute to creating an enabling environment for businesses attracting investments and promoting social inclusion (Baland, et al., 2020). Sound institutions also foster economic stability and reduce income inequality.

3. CHALLENGES TO INCLUSIVE GROWTH IN NIGERIA

In Nigeria one of the challenges to inclusive growth is the high level of corruption within the government and public institutions. In Nigeria, corruption not only diverts public resources out of investment in productive sectors but also undermines the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery (Yinusa, Aworinde, & Odusanya, 2020). Another challenge is the lack of access to finance particularly for small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs). Access to finance restrictions, limit the growth of SMEs and hinders business creation and economic development (Egbide, Samuel, & Babajide, 2015).

Weak Institutional Framework

A weak institutional framework has been identified as one of the major obstacles to inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. Empirical studies have shown that weak institutions hinder economic activities, discourage investment and restrict entrepreneurship. Law, Lim, & Ismail, (2013) found that weak institutions in Nigeria impede the effective implementation of economic policies and regulatory frameworks leading to corruption and rent-seeking behavior. Similarly, Yuan, & He, (2011) revealed that weak institutions characterized by inadequate property rights protection and an unreliable legal system discourage foreign direct investment.

Corruption and Rent-Seeking Behavior

Corruption and rent-seeking behavior in Nigeria are major barriers to inclusive growth and development. Empirical studies have demonstrated the detrimental effects of corruption on economic performance and social welfare. Rent-seeking behavior which involves individuals or groups seeking economic benefits by manipulating the political and economic system leads to inefficiency, misallocation of resources and economic distortions. Noncompetitive procurement processes for example have been identified as a common avenue for rent-seeking activities in Nigeria (Abilor, Olawole, & Adeniran, 2020).

Lack of Access to Basic Services and Infrastructure

The lack of access to basic services and infrastructure is an important challenge in Nigeria's quest for inclusive growth and development. Inadequate access to basic services such as

healthcare education and clean water hinders human capital development and perpetuates poverty. The poor state of infrastructure in Nigeria, particularly roads and electricity, has negative implications for productivity and economic growth (Okonkwo, Kalu & Nwosu, 2018). This lack of access to basic services and infrastructure disproportionately impacts rural areas and marginalized communities exacerbating existing inequalities. In order to achieve inclusive growth and development it is imperative for the Nigerian government and relevant stakeholders to prioritize investments in improving access to basic services and infrastructure across the country.

Empirical Studies

Empirical studies provide valuable insights into the relationship between institutions and inclusive growth in Nigeria. Olanrewaju, Aremo, & Binuyo, (2020) analyzed the role of institutions in promoting inclusive growth in Nigeria. The findings revealed that weak institutions characterized by corruption and lack of transparency hindered inclusive growth by inhibiting investment, promoting inequality and limiting access to basic services. Ogujiuba, & Alehile, (2011) conducted a comprehensive analysis of the impact of institutions on inclusive growth in Nigeria. The study highlighted that good institutions such as strong property rights protection and efficient government encouraged inclusive growth by stimulating investment and decreasing income inequality providing greater access to education and healthcare.

Ajayi et al. (2018) examined the impact of governance institutions on economic growth. The researchers used panel data analysis for the period 1985-2015 to investigate the relationship between governance institutions and economic growth in Nigeria. The findings indicate that governance institutions have a statistically significant positive effect on economic growth. The finding suggested that institutions such as political stability, property rights protection and control of corruption are significant determinants of economic growth. The study provides empirical evidence supporting the idea that governance institutions play a critical role in promoting economic growth in Nigeria. This suggests that policymakers should focus on implementing effective governance mechanisms to stimulate long-term economic growth.

The empirical studies on inclusive growth in Nigeria have yielded significant findings and implications. Fayyaz, (2022) found that there is a positive relationship between institutional quality and inclusive growth. They found that the improvement in key institutions such as government rule of law and regulation quality can bring to inclusive growth by reducing corruption, improving economic stability and attracting foreign investment. Also, Yinusa, Aworinde, & Odusanya, (2020) concluded that investing in human capital and improving access to quality education and healthcare can also promote inclusive growth.

4. STRATEGIES FOR PROMOTING INCLUSIVE GROWTH IN NIGERIA

First, it is important to address the issue of corruption which has long been a barrier to economic development in the country. Abiloro, Olawole, & Adeniran, (2020) found that corruption substantially hampers inclusive growth by diverting resources away from productive sectors of the economy. Also efforts should be made to strengthen anti-corruption institutions and improve governance mechanisms. Furthermore it is essential to increase access to quality education and healthcare. Obayelu, & Awoyemi, (2012) suggests that investing in human capital through education and healthcare is crucial for inclusive growth. Policies that promote financial inclusion such as expanding access to credit for small and medium-sized enterprises have been found to be effective in promoting inclusive growth in other countries.

Strengthening Institutional Capacity and Governance

Institutions play a crucial role in promoting inclusive development and development in Nigeria. Empirical studies have shown that strong institutions characterized by transparency accountability and the rule of law are associated with higher levels of economic development and reduced inequality. Good government institutions are positively associated with economic growth and development (Ming-ru, 2007; Natkhov, & Boranukov, 2010). These studies highlight the importance of improving the capacity of institutions to provide public goods and services, promote transparency and accountability and enforce the rule of law. For example Haan, (2007) have found that countries with good institutional quality have higher levels of economic growth. Natkhov, & Boranukov, (2010) find that better governance quality leads to higher levels of investment increasing productivity and a good economic outcome. Therefore addressing institutional weaknesses and strengthening governance frameworks is essential for fostering inclusive growth and development in Nigeria.

Enhancing Transparency and Accountability: This is crucial for promoting inclusive growth in Nigeria. Empirical studies have shown that more transparency leads to higher trust in government institutions. This in turn improves the effectiveness and efficiency of the public administration. Transparency is also associated with successful governance outcomes such as reduced corruption levels and increased public participation (Yinusa, Aworinde, & Odusanya, 2020). Accountability mechanisms such as the establishment of anti-corruption agencies have been found to significantly reduce levels of corruption. It is therefore expected that enhancing Transparency and accountability in Nigeria would bring to the development of strong and good institutions which are essential for inclusive and sustainable growth.

Promoting rule of law and reducing corruption: Combating corruption is crucial for promoting equity and reducing poverty in Nigeria. In addition research has shown that countries with stronger rule of law institutions experience higher levels of economic growth

and better development outcomes (Okonkwo, Kalu & Nwosu, 2018; Ogujiuba, & Alehile, 2011). Therefore strengthening the rule of law and addressing corruption should be key priority for policy makers in order to promote inclusive growth and development in Nigeria.

Investing in Human Capital Development

Investing in human capital development is necessary for long-term economic growth and development. Studies have shown that countries with higher levels of human capital have higher levels of productivity and income.

Improving Access to Quality Education and Healthcare: Improving access to quality education and healthcare has been identified as an important component for promoting inclusive growth. Access to quality education is linked to improved economic outcomes as individuals with higher levels of education are more likely to secure higher paying jobs and bring to productivity and innovation (Lian-cheng, 2005). Furthermore access to quality healthcare has been shown to reduce inequalities in health outcomes and improve overall wellbeing (Amin, 2020). By investing in education and healthcare infrastructure Nigeria can improve social mobility Enhance human capital development and foster inclusive growth in the long run.

Enhancing Skills Training and Entrepreneurship Programs: One way to promote inclusive growth and development in Nigeria is through strengthening skills training and entrepreneurship programs. Several empirical studies have underscored the importance of skills development in improving economic outcomes for individuals and the society. Gathungu, (2013) found that individuals who participated in skills training programs were more likely to get formal work and earn higher wages. By equipping individuals with the necessary skills and knowledge to take part in entrepreneurial activities there is a greater likelihood of creating employment opportunities unlocking innovation and fostering economic diversification. Therefore, it is imperative for policymakers to prioritize the enhancement of skills training and entrepreneurship programs to drive inclusive growth and development in Nigeria.

Infrastructure Development and Access to Basic Services

Empirical studies have indicated a positive relationship between infrastructure development and economic growth. Menendez, (1991) found that improvements in infrastructure such as roads electricity and water supply have a significant impact on economic growth. Access to basic services such as healthcare education and clean water is essential to poverty reduction and human development. Therefore, investing in infrastructure development and ensuring access to basic services are essential strategies for achieving inclusive growth and development in Nigeria.

Investing in Transportation, Energy, and Telecommunications:

Investing in transportation energy and telecommunications has been identified as an important factor for fostering inclusive growth and development. Improving transportation infrastructure such as the building and maintenance of roads and highways facilitates the movement of goods and people and thus increasing economic activities and productivity. Enhancing access to reliable and affordable energy sources is also associated with higher economic growth rates and better living standards (Adetola, 2014). The development of robust and effective telecommunication networks has been found to contribute to economic development by promoting access to information enabling e-commerce and facilitating communication (Leong, 2005).

Expanding Access to Clean Water, Sanitation, and Housing: Empirical studies have demonstrated the positive impact of access to clean water on health outcomes and economic productivity. For example, Hunter, et al., (2001). found that access to clean water reduced the incidence of waterborne diseases and improved overall health in rural communities in Nigeria. Also, Wami, Fisher, Akpilla, & Radu, (2021) showed that improved access to sanitation facilities improved school attendance rates and improved educational outcomes among children in Nigeria. Access to sufficient housing is crucial for social and economic development as it contributes to human capital formation and poverty reduction. Expanding the access to clean water sanitation and housing is therefore crucial to the promotion of inclusive growth and development in Nigeria.

5. CONCLUSION

The empirical studies reviewed in this study have provided insights into the relationship between inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. The study suggests that institutions play an important role in promoting inclusive growth and development by providing conducive environment for economic activities, ensuring a fair distribution of resources and upholding the rule of law. The study suggests that an effective legal framework, transparent governance and strong property rights protection are essential to attract foreign direct investment. Similarly, inclusive institutions such as those promoting access to education and healthcare tend to have positive effects on poverty reduction and overall development.

Key Findings and Policy Recommendations

This investigation into the relationship between institutions inclusive growth and development in Nigeria has produced several key findings. First, studies have consistently identified weak governance and corruption as major barriers to inclusive growth and development in Nigeria. Second, research has highlighted the importance of institutional reforms in promoting inclusive growth and development in Nigeria Osuntogun (2015), Nwokolo (2014) and Oni (2013). These studies emphasize the need for policies that enhance transparency, accountability and the rule of

law as well as better the business environment to attract investment and to encourage economic activity.

Based on these findings, policy recommendations were made to include:

- a. Promoting good governance and anti-corruption efforts
- b. Promote institutional reforms and fostering an enabling environment for private sector-led growth.

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